

CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS OF GENETIC ALGORITHM

(Statistical and Computational Approach)

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Abstract—Genetic algorithm (Holland, 1975) is a well-known heuristic search method. Genetic Algorithms (GA) have been successfully applied for the solution optimization problems. Convergence is an important issue in Genetic Algorithms. There has been a lot of research activities in the field of convergence of Genetic Algorithms. However, no mathematical proof is available for their convergence. In this research we have approached the problem from a statistical and computational perspective.

Keywords- Genetic Algorithm, Convergence ,cross over ,mutation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The convergence of genetic algorithms is one of the most challenging theoretical issues in the evolutionary computation area. Several researchers explored this problem from different perspectives [2]. Goldberg and Segrest [3,5] provided a finite Markov chain analysis of genetic algorithm (finite population, reproduction and mutation only). Davis and Principe [2] investigated a possibility of extrapolation of the existing theoretical foundation of the simulated annealing algorithm onto a Markov chain genetic algorithm model. Eiben , Aarts, and Van Hee [2] have proposed an abstract genetic algorithm which unifies genetic algorithms and simulated annealing; a Markov chain analysis on such an abstract genetic algorithm is discussed and conditions implying that the evolution process finds an optimum with probability are given. Kingdon [2] investigated starting points, convergence and the class of problems genetic algorithms find hard to solve . The notion of competing schemata is generalized and the probability of convergence of such schemata is given. Several researchers considered also various definitions of deceptive problems [5]. Rudolph proved[6] that a classical genetic algorithm never converges to the global optimum,

but modified versions, which maintain the best solution in the population do.

One possible approach for explaining the convergence properties of genetic algorithm might be based on Banach fix point theorem [2]. It provides an intuitive explanation of a convergence of GAs (without elitist model); the only requirement is that there should be an improvement in subsequent populations(not necessarily improvement of the best individual).

Banach fix point theorem deals with contractive mappings on metric spaces. It states that any such a mapping f has a unique fix point, i.e., an element x such that $f(x) = x$.

Fix point techniques are generally accepted as a powerful tool for defining semantics of computations.

Most of these research work have assumed strong limitation conditions .this research aims to soften these limitations.

II. A BRIEF HISTORY ON GENETIC ALGORITHM

Genetic Algorithm (GA) initiated and developed in early 1970s by John Holland is unorthodox search and optimization algorithm ,which mimic some of the processes of natural evolution .GA has been successfully applied for the solution of a variety of problems such as optimization ,NP problems, scheduling ,and etc.

A .Simple generational genetic algorithm procedure:

- Choose the initial *population* of individuals
- Evaluate the *fitness* of each individual in that population

- Repeat on this *generation* until termination (time limit, sufficient fitness achieved, etc.):
 - Select the best-fit individuals for *reproduction*.
 - Breed* new individuals through *crossover* and *mutation* operations (fig 1,2) to give birth to *offspring*.
 - Evaluate the individual fitness of new individuals.
 - Replace least-fit population with new individuals.

FIGURE 1 A diagram for genetic algorithm procedure

FIGURE 2 tree-model cross over

FIGURE 3 general cross over

B. Applications of genetic algorithms

This is the most important list of Genetic Algorithm (GA) applications:

- computer-automated design
- Bioinformatics.
- Chemical kinetics (gas and solid phases)
- Clustering. Using genetic algorithms to optimize a wide range of different fit-functions.
- Code-breaking, using the GA to search large solution spaces of ciphers for the one correct decryption.
- Configuration applications, particularly physics applications of optimal molecule configurations for particular systems .
- Container loading optimization.
- Control engineering.
- Data Center/Server Farm.
- Design of water distribution systems.
- Distributed computer network topologies.
- Electronic circuit design, known as evolvable hardware.
- File allocation for a distributed system.
- Finding hardware bugs.
- Game theory equilibrium resolution.
- Genetic Algorithm for Rule Set Production
- Economics
- Scheduling applications, including job-shop scheduling. The objective being to schedule jobs in a sequence-dependent or non-sequence-dependent setup environment in order to maximize the volume of production

while minimizing penalties such as tardiness.

- Learning robot behavior using genetic algorithms.
- Learning fuzzy rule base using genetic algorithms.

C. Advantages and disadvantages of Genetic algorithm

Genetic algorithm has a number of advantages as an example it can quickly scan a vast solution set ; Convergence problem as mentioned in part I of this paper is a disadvantage of Genetic algorithm ,so the main objective of this paper is analysis of convergence properties from statistical and computational perspective.

III. STATISTICAL CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS OF GENETIC ALGORITHM

For convergence analysis of Genetic Algorithm we consider three states of encoding:

- Binary encoding (0,1).
- Real encoding (0 – 9).
- Alphabet encoding (A – Z)

Assume that n_0, n_1, \dots, n_k is a population in a GA system ,and (x_0, y_0) are 2 random offspring ,(x₀,y₀) are the first selection.

If a set of different GA operators are applied N/2 times(where N is a very large number)on the (x_0, y_0) then n_0 is generated f_0 , n_1 is generated f_1, \dots, n_k is generated f_k

Where: $N/2 = f_0 + f_1 + \dots + f_k$

We are going to prove f_0, f_1, \dots, f_k have uniform distribution .this lead us to the convergence of GA.

IV. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Case study 1

In this case study we have considered binary encoding and put $n=8$ (population is {0,1,...,255}) and N=10000 ,so the frequency of observed all offspring $(f_0, f_1, \dots, f_{255})$ where

$100000 = f_0 + f_1 + \dots + f_k$) have uniform distribution see Fig 4.

Figure 4. Convergence of Genetic Algorithm 100000 with use of data.

case study 2

In this case study we have considered binary encoding and put $n=8$ (population is {0,1,...,255}) and N=10000 ,so we perform several cross over on primary population, N times in order to produce other offspring suppose that f_i is the frequency of the observed i in N test ,as Fig.5 Shows the accumulation of blue spots on the horizontal axis indicates $f_i=0$,its means too much members of population are not produced (about %75).

the same test is done with using mutation ,as pink spots in

Fig.5 shows that all members of the population (0..255) are produced monotonously ,so the obtained results of the above test are written as follows:

- if too much cross over are performed on a primary offspring, some offspring of the population will not produce .
- cross over can not provide the convergence alone and mutation is able to provide the convergence alone.

FIGURE 5. Comparing cross over and mutation in Convergence of Genetic Algorithm with use of 10000 data.

V. CONCLUSION

Genetic Algorithm has high ability for solving optimization problems. The convergence is one of the most challenging theoretical issues in the genetic algorithms .

In this paper we have approached the convergence of genetic algorithm from a computational and Statistical perspective .Our research have not completed about this problem and we are carrying our studies on the other aspect of convergence of Genetic Algorithm.

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VII. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Ragasekaran , " Genetic Algorithm Neural Network Fuzzy Logic ", New Delhi,2006.
- [2]. Zbigniew Michalewicz , "Genetic Algorithms+ Data Structures= Evolution Programs", New York,1992.
- [3]. Goldberg, D.E. and Segrest, P , "Finite Markov Chain Analysis of Genetic Algorithms",1995.
- [4]. Davis, L., (Editor), "Handbook of Genetic Algorithms, Van Nostrand Reinhold", New York,1991.
- [5].Goldberg,D.E., "Messy Genetic Algorithm motivation Analysis",1989.

[6].G.Rudolph,,Convergence Properties of Evolutionary Algorithms,1997.

[7] S.Ghanbari , M.Khosrokhani, "A New Approach to Evolutionary Algorithms - Bisected Algorithm",WSEAS conf, Crete , Greece ,Jul 2008.

[8]S. Ghanbari and M.Khosrokhani, "Statisticalapproach to Convergence of Genetic Algorithms " ,OR2009,Babolsar ,Iran, 2009.